

Simultaneous Acquisition of Analog Signals with Two ADC Converters via Direct Memory Access (DMA) in a Prototype Based on the dsPIC33FJ256GP706A

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Abstract—This article describes the development of a prototype for simultaneous acquisition of analog signals using two analog-to-digital converters (ADC) with data transfer via Direct Memory Access (DMA), implemented on the dsPIC33FJ256GP706A Digital Signal Controller from Microchip Technology. The system constitutes a fundamental stage for the construction of a digital Lock-In amplifier, in which synchronous and continuous reading of two independent analog channels is a necessary condition. The firmware was developed in C language using the MPLAB C30 compiler, and the sampled data were transmitted via asynchronous serial RS-232 interface for graphical visualization on a host computer. Sinusoidal, digital, and triangular signals were applied at three distinct frequencies — 120 Hz, 525 Hz, and 1178 Hz — with an amplitude of 1.1 Vpp, demonstrating the feasibility of simultaneous, complete, and lossless acquisition on both channels. The results show that the use of DMA in Ping-Pong mode, combined with hardware timers as the sampling clock source, ensures stable periodicity and frees the CPU for processing tasks, confirming the suitability of the platform for the development of the proposed digital Lock-In amplifier.

Index Terms—Direct Memory Access. ADC. dsPIC33F. Digital Lock-In. Data Acquisition. Embedded Systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The detection of low-amplitude electrical signals in noisy environments is a central problem in scientific and industrial instrumentation. The Lock-In amplifier constitutes the classical solution, using synchronous detection — that is, the multiplication of the input signal by a reference of the same frequency followed by low-pass filtering — to extract coherent components even when their amplitude is far below the noise floor (Meade, 1983; Scofield, 1994). The digital implementation of the Lock-In amplifier expands flexibility, repeatability, and integration with computational systems compared to traditional analog approaches (Luda et al., 2019).

To enable a digital Lock-In amplifier, synchronous acquisition of at least two analog channels, corresponding to the signal and the reference, with precise timing is essential. Relying on the CPU for individual transfers would compromise synchrony and system performance (Tanenbaum and Bos,

2014). The use of Direct Memory Access allows the ADC to transfer data directly to memory, notifying the CPU only at the end of sample blocks, thereby preserving temporal integrity and processing efficiency (Barr and Massa, 2006).

The dsPIC33FJ256GP706A from Microchip Technology, classified as a Digital Signal Controller, integrates 16-bit microcontroller and DSP resources, including multiply-and-accumulate instructions, as well as two independent ADC modules, multiple DMA channels, and timers (Microchip Technology, 2011). The presence of two ADCs associated with distinct DMA channels enables truly simultaneous acquisition, avoiding phase shifts introduced by time-division multiplexing (Kester, 2005).

The literature demonstrates the feasibility of using low-cost DSCs and DSPs in precision instrumentation. Yang et al. (2012) achieved performance comparable to commercial equipment; Maya et al. (2019) highlighted the role of DMA in temporal integrity; Michels et al. (2010) demonstrated the importance of coordination between DMA and timers for sampling stability.

This article presents the design, implementation, and experimental validation of a simultaneous dual-channel ADC acquisition prototype with DMA, discussing its software architecture, experimental results, and the feasibility of the solution for application in a digital Lock-In amplifier.

2. METHODOLOGY

The prototype was developed on the dsPICDEM kit from Microchip Technology, using the dsPIC33FJ256GP706A in a TQFP-100 package. The device operates with an F_{CY} of 40 MHz, obtained from an external XT-type crystal and an internal PLL configured for F_{osc} of 165.6 MHz, as parameterized in the firmware. The watchdog timer was disabled via fuse, a common practice during the prototyping phase (Ibrahim, 2008).

Acquisition uses both ADC modules simultaneously and independently. ADC1 samples pin AN0 and ADC2 samples

pin AN1, both configured as analog inputs. The converters operate with 10-bit resolution, a system-derived clock, and automatic sampling triggered by a timer, ensuring deterministic periodicity and the absence of software-associated jitter (Michels et al., 2010). Timer3 triggers ADC1 and Timer5 triggers ADC2, both with $PR = 79$, resulting in a sampling rate of 500 kHz for F_{CY} of 40 MHz. Each ADC operates in scan mode with a single selected channel.

Data transfer is performed by DMA channels DMA0 and DMA1, associated respectively with ADC1 and ADC2, configured in peripheral indirect addressing mode and Ping-Pong operation. This mode uses two alternating buffers, allowing one to be filled while the other is processed, ensuring continuous acquisition without data overwriting (Microchip Technology, 2011). Each buffer contains 128 samples, allocated in DMA memory with 512-byte alignment as required by the architecture. The transfer count was configured for 128 samples per block, with the peripheral address registers pointing to ADC1BUF0 and ADC2BUF0. The DMA request numbers were defined according to the datasheet (Microchip Technology, 2011).

The interrupt service routines `_DMA0Interrupt` and `_DMA1Interrupt` are executed at the end of each transferred block. Each ISR identifies the available buffer, copies the 128 samples to 512-position circular buffers, updates the index with boundary control, alternates the active buffer via XOR operation, and clears the interrupt flag. The use of a static local variable for buffer control preserves state between successive calls, as recommended for interrupt service routines (Barr and Massa, 2006). An LED is toggled at each interrupt as a debugging resource.

Communication with the computer is performed via UART1 at 115200 baud, 8 bits, no parity. Upon request via a received character, the system temporarily disables the DMA interrupts, transmits the 512 samples of each channel with resolution adjustment for serial transmission, sends the termination sequence, and re-enables the DMA, ensuring data coherence during transmission (Axelson, 2007). For experimental validation, an external function generator was connected simultaneously to pins AN0 and AN1, and data visualization on the PC was performed by software developed in Delphi 7.0.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system was tested with three waveforms — sinusoidal, digital, and triangular — at frequencies of 120 Hz, 525 Hz, and 1178 Hz, all with 1.1 Vpp. These conditions allowed the evaluation of system performance at different ratios between signal frequency and sampling rate, well within the Nyquist criterion (Oppenheim and Schaffer, 2010). In all cases, the signals sampled by ADC1 and ADC2 presented identical waveform, amplitude, and phase, confirming the simultaneity of acquisition and the absence of inter-channel phase shift. Figures 1, 2, and 3 present the results for 525 Hz.

In Figure 1, the sinusoidal signal sampled simultaneously on both channels shows complete overlap across the 512 samples, demonstrating synchrony and absence of differential delay.

Fig. 1. Sinusoidal signal applied to ADC1 and ADC2 at 525 Hz with 1.1 Vpp.

Figure 2 presents the digital signal at the same frequency. The adequate reproduction of abrupt transitions indicates sufficient bandwidth for high-order harmonic components and the absence of distortion introduced by the DMA. The equivalence of gain and offset between the converters is consistent with the expected behavior for ADCs integrated in the same device (Kester, 2005).

Fig. 2. Digital signal applied to ADC1 and ADC2 at 525 Hz with 1.1 Vpp.

Figure 3 shows the triangular signal, a waveform suited for evaluating converter linearity (Kester, 2005). The ramps exhibit linear and symmetric behavior on both channels, confirming the integrity of conversion and timing.

Results at 120 Hz and 1178 Hz maintained the same behavior, confirming correct operation across the entire tested range, below the configured Nyquist limit (Oppenheim and Schaffer, 2010).

Regarding software architecture, the Ping-Pong DMA mode ensured continuous acquisition. While one physical buffer is being filled, the other is transferred to the application's circular buffer, eliminating gaps between consecutive blocks (Michels et al., 2010). The use of 128-sample blocks, totaling 512 per acquisition, represents a compromise between interrupt frequency and latency, as discussed in the embedded systems

Fig. 3. Triangular signal applied to ADC1 and ADC2 at 525 Hz with 1.1 Vpp.

literature (Barr and Massa, 2006; Ibrahim, 2008).

Serial transmission at 115200 baud constitutes the system's primary bottleneck. Sending 1024 bytes requires approximately 89 ms, during which interrupts remain disabled. For the Lock-In application, in which only processed results would be transmitted, this bottleneck is reduced (Yang et al., 2012). Request-driven communication avoids race conditions between acquisition and transmission (Axelson, 2007). The two-bit right shift applied before transmission reduces resolution from 10 to 8 bits, which is sufficient for functional validation but inadequate for precision measurements, which require full preservation of the converter resolution (Kester, 2005).

It is concluded that the prototype is capable of simultaneous, continuous, and deterministic acquisition of two analog channels with low CPU load, meeting the requirements for the future implementation of synchronous detection in a digital Lock-In amplifier (Luda et al., 2019; Scofield, 1994).

The source code for this research is available for download at: <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/dma>.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Tests with sinusoidal, square, and triangular signals at frequencies of 120 Hz, 525 Hz, and 1178 Hz confirmed the effective simultaneity of sampling, with no differences in waveform, amplitude, or phase between the channels — an essential condition for the future implementation of the digital Lock-In amplifier. The dual-DMA architecture in Ping-Pong mode eliminated CPU load during acquisition, allowing the processor to remain available for real-time digital signal processing, a fundamental requirement for synchronous detection. As future work, the integration of the digital Lock-In algorithm into the firmware is planned, along with the implementation of serial transmission preserving the full 10-bit resolution and the evaluation of system performance in terms of signal-to-noise ratio and dynamic range, in comparison with commercial solutions.

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